

Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie

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CCSA – Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas
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CCSA – Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas
Programa de Pós-Graduação em Controladoria e Finanças
Empresariais

NORMA OU MARCO REGULATÓRIO

Resposta à Audiência Pública: CONTRIBUTION TO THE
AUDITOR REPORTING IMPLEMENTATION WORKING
GROUP (ARIWG)

Maria Patricia Agostineto
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Como referenciar:

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Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas

Linha de Pesquisa: Finanças, regulação contábil e tributária

Projeto de pesquisa: Cérebro, Cognição e Comportamento: teoria e aplicação para inovação em negócios - PrInt

Produto Técnico-Tecnológico: Norma ou marco regulatório

Demanda espontânea: resposta à consulta pública do Auditor Reporting Implementation Working Group (ARIWG)

Organização: Demanda do Auditor Reporting Implementation Group, produzido pela dissertação da aluna no PPGCFTG da Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie

Descrição do PPT: Resposta à consulta pública do Auditor Reporting Implementation Working Group (ARIWG).

Divulgação da Produção: A resposta à consulta pública foi enviada como resposta ao questionamento do AIRIWG. Sendo esta resposta um relatório derivado de uma dissertação, está disponível na plataforma Zenodo.

Aderência (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. O relatório técnico é resultado de uma ampla discussão de normas contábeis desenvolvida pela aluna junto à diretores e conselheiros de empresas, consistindo em um resultado de formação de pessoas (alunos de graduação e pos graduação) e também proposições técnicas que podem afetar a todas as organizações que está sujeita a auditoria.

Impacto Potencial: Médio. O resultado desta resposta técnica resultará em alterações das normas contábeis com potencial de impacto para todas empresas de auditoria no Brasil e no mundo.

Impacto Realizado: Médio. O impacto de uma alteração de norma deve ser observado no futuro, com a implementação das sugestões feitas por essa pesquisa. Dessa forma, só será possível medir o impacto na efetiva implementação das alterações sugeridas.

Inovação (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Média. Uma norma contábil para auditoria é sempre importante por se tratar de asseguramento das informações. Portanto, a implementação efetiva desta norma sugere uma inovação para a área contábil e de produção de informações confiáveis para a estas entidades.

Complexidade (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Média. O produto requer um conhecimento técnico bastante abrangente em normas contábeis para que seja elaborado uma resposta técnica e cujo tema foi debatido junto a profissionais de mercado, com diversas áreas de conhecimento técnico empresarial. Dessa forma, entende-se que a complexidade deste produto é média.

Aplicabilidade (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. Aplicabilidade para todas as empresas de auditoria.

Abrangência Potencial (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. A norma terá aplicabilidade em todo o território nacional e internacional.

Abrangência realizada (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. A norma terá aplicabilidade em todo o território nacional e internacional.

Replicabilidade (Restrita, Irrestrita ou Escalável): Irrestrita

Resposta à Audiência Pública - CONTRIBUTION TO THE AUDITOR REPORTING IMPLEMENTATION WORKING GROUP (ARIWG)

RESUMO

IAASB started the Post-Implementation Review process (“PIR process”) of the new auditor’s report in July 2020 with the disclosure of a first activity that comprised a formal international survey with many stakeholders: investors, regulators, preparers, those in charge of governance, auditors and their representative professional bodies, regulatory accounting bodies and other users of the financial statements. At that time, it also informed that, in addition to the above-mentioned formal survey, it would organize meetings with specific groups of users, as well as a review of academic studies on the new auditor’s report. As a form of contributing to the PIR process of the new auditor’s report that is in progress, the master student in Controllershship and Corporate Finance, Maria Patrícia Agostineto, together with her advisor, Prof. Dr. Liliane Cristina Segura from Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie (Mackenzie Presbyterian University), of São Paulo, Brazil, would like to share with IAASB’s working group the summarized result of an academic study on the new auditor’s report that investigated the “Perception of board members on the relevance of the new expanded audit report for the improvement of the quality of information.”.

Palavras-chave: auditing, standards, IAASB, quality of information

Response to Public Consultation - Contribution to the Auditor Reporting Implementation Working Group (ARIWG)

ABSTRACT

IAASB started the Post-Implementation Review process (“PIR process”) of the new auditor’s report in July 2020 with the disclosure of a first activity that comprised a formal international survey with many stakeholders: investors, regulators, preparers, those in charge of governance, auditors and their representative professional bodies, regulatory accounting bodies and other users of the financial statements. At that time, it also informed that, in addition to the above-mentioned formal survey, it would organize meetings with specific groups of users, as well as a review of academic studies on the new auditor’s report. As a form of contributing to the PIR process of the new auditor’s report that is in progress, the master student in Controllershship and Corporate Finance, Maria Patrícia Agostineto, together with her advisor, Prof. Dr. Liliane Cristina Segura from Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie (Mackenzie Presbyterian University), of São Paulo, Brazil, would like to share with IAASB’s working group the summarized result of an academic study on the new auditor’s report that investigated the “Perception of board members on the relevance of the new expanded audit report for the improvement of the quality of information.”.

Keywords: auditing, standards, IAASB, quality of information

Como referenciar:

Agostineto, M. P.; Segura, L C (2021). Resposta à Audiência Pública: CONTRIBUTION TO THE AUDITOR REPORTING IMPLEMENTATION WORKING GROUP (ARIWG). Norma ou Marco Regulatório. PPGCFTG da Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie. Grupo de Estudos em IFRS DOI/ 10.5281/zenodo.14982562

International Assurance and Auditing Standards Board for Accountants (IAASB) 05/04/2021

São Paulo, April 05, 2021

To the
International Assurance and Auditing Standards Board for Accountants (IAASB)
545 Fifth Avenue, 14th Floor
New York, NY 10017
USA

Reference: Contribution to the Auditor Reporting Implementation Working Group (ARIWG)

Dear Sirs and/or Madams,

IAASB started the Post-Implementation Review process (“PIR process”) of the new auditor’s report in July 2020 with the disclosure of a first activity that comprised a formal international survey with many stakeholders: investors, regulators, preparers, those in charge of governance, auditors and their representative professional bodies, regulatory accounting bodies and other users of the financial statements. At that time, it also informed that, in addition to the above-mentioned formal survey, it would organize meetings with specific groups of users, as well as a review of academic studies on the new auditor’s report.

As a form of contributing to the PIR process of the new auditor’s report that is in progress, the master student in Controllershship and Corporate Finance, Maria Patrícia Agostineto, together with her advisor, Prof. Dr. Liliane Cristina Segura from *Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie* (Mackenzie Presbyterian University), of São Paulo, Brazil, would like to share with IAASB’s working group the summarized result of an academic study on the new auditor’s report that investigated the “Perception of board members on the relevance of the new expanded audit report for the improvement of the quality of information.”

The survey technique applied was the extensive direct observation – questionnaires were sent to those charged with governance of companies in Brazil and answered in writing without the presence of the surveyor. This questionnaire has been prepared based on the analysis of previous studies and on the survey, material disclosed by IAASB in July 2020 called “Auditor Reporting Post-Implementation Review – Stakeholder Survey.”

The questionnaire was answered by governance members of large-sized companies in Brazil and the results could be valuable for the decisions of the above-mentioned working group, taking into consideration the background and skills of the respondents of this survey.

Forty-seven questionnaires were answered, which is equivalent to 15.3% of the total questionnaires sent. The responding group of board members is mostly composed of men older than 50 years of age (72.3%), although there is a significant portion of female respondents (27.7%) serving on boards of directors, mainly in publicly listed companies (68.1%). The responding board members are experienced people with a high degree of education reported, and 100% of the respondents have bachelor’s degrees and 62% have postgraduate degrees. With respect to the field of education, the results indicate a concentration in courses in the financial field (72.3%).

Therefore, the report below indicates the perception of board members of large-sized publicly listed and closely held companies in Brazil, which is a great contribution to your analysis and consideration.

The report is divided in three parts: General perceptions of the respondents on the auditor’s report; Perceptions of the communication of the Key Audit Matters (“KAM”) and Perceptions of the disclosure of voluntary additional information.

General perceptions of the respondents on the auditor’s report

1. What is the extension of your reading of the auditor’s report?

The answer of the board members showed the importance of the auditor's report to this analyzed group. More than 80% of the respondents read the entire auditor's report and the remaining 20%, who noted that they read part of the report, takes into account, in their regular reading, in addition to the auditor's opinion, the key audit matters, which is a new development identified by IAASB starting in 2016.

2. Does the new auditor's report provide better understanding and transparency for the work carried out by the independent auditor and their responsibilities?

The high percentage of agreement in the answers to the question related to the understanding of the audit performed (95.7%) confirms that, in the opinion of the responding board members, the new expanded report reached the objective of being more informative, providing increased clarity on the audit process and on the responsibilities of each party – management and independent auditor.

3. Did the new auditor's report positively change your perception of the quality of the audit performed?

The respondents mostly indicated that the new auditor's report positively changed their perception of the quality of the audit performed (80.9%), which may be explained by the fact that, as in charged with governance, they maintain a more robust communication process with the auditors.

4. In your view, to what extent is the following information provided in the new auditor's report useful?

- **Communication of the key audit matters.**
- **Changes to the presentation of the auditor's report.**
- **When applicable, a separate section related to going concern.**

The respondents confirmed the importance of the communication of KAM and of the greater prominence given to the going concern matter in a separate section to address

the topic in the auditor's report. Although the respondents have expressed their agreement with the other changes made to the presentation of the report, the agreement with this third category was smaller. In the view of 75% of the board members, the communication of KAM was the most significant change that took place. By adding the 19% of the board members that consider the change useful, we reach an agreement of 94%. It is the communication of KAM that makes the auditor's report more informative by highlighting more significant matters in the audit for the year in the auditor's judgment.

The portion of the respondents that considered that the three main changes mentioned before had a limited value or are not useful (6%, 20% and 4%, respectively), is mainly composed of board members that are not accountants.

Perceptions of the communication of the Key Audit Matters ("KAM")

5. Based on the reports that you have been reading, has the information communicated in KAM met your expectations?

Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:

- **The description of KAM is concise, that is, properly summarized.**
- **The description of KAM is understandable, without being excessively technical.**
- **The description of KAM is specific to the entity, without generic and standardized wording.**
- **The communication of KAM has changed the way this matter had been handled and disclosed in the notes to the financial statements.**

The answers regarding the meeting of the expectations indicate that the form of communication of KAM fully satisfies only 36.2% of the respondents. For 57.4% of the board members, the communication partially meets their expectations. The percentage of 6% of the respondents that was indifferent or with some degree of disagreement that it met their expectations is mainly composed of board members that are not accountants. To understand the reasons why it did not fully meet their expectations, it

is necessary to analyze the answers on the readability of KAM.

- i. **Summarization of the matter:** although the description of KAM is a matter of the auditor's professional judgment, the answers of the board members indicate that there is room to improve the description of KAM because the KAM are not always presented in a short and balanced way so as to allow a proper understanding of the reasons this matter had been considered of being of greatest importance in the audit.
 - ii. **Language used:** the answers indicate that the auditors continue to use technical terms that make understanding of the matter difficult by users that do not have reasonable audit knowledge.
 - iii. **Standardization:** the answers indicate that the risk of standardized wording has been materializing, pushing the KAM away from its primary purpose of being useful and relevant for the users of the auditor's report on the financial statements.
6. **Based on the audit reports you have been reading, which matter do you consider more relevant and useful to be communicated as KAM?**
- **When related to accounting estimates.**
 - **When related to a higher risk of material misstatement.**
 - **When related to facts and transactions that took place in the year.**

For 77% of the board members, the matter that most interests those charged with governance is related to the higher risk of material misstatement in the financial statements. The other matters (accounting estimates and transactions for the year) are practically tied at 49% and 43%, respectively. By adding the two percentages of agreement (total + partial), we have 96%, 94% and 92%, respectively, but still with a preference to the material misstatement topic, which does not diminish the importance of the accounting estimates topic, taking into consideration the high degree of judgment and assumptions adopted by management that depend on macroeconomic conditions, among others, which, if changed, will have a significant impact on the company's balance sheets.

7. Has the communication of KAM affected internal processes such as, for example, the improvement of the internal control, the preparation of the financial statements by management and the interactions of the auditor with management and the corporate governance bodies after the adoption of the new auditor's report?

For 32% of the board members, there was an improvement in the disclosures (and associated internal control) in the financial statements when a matter was communicated as KAM in the auditor's report. For 40% of the board members who partially agreed with this, we infer that, for the companies that have good governance practices, with a proper level of disclosure, there has not been a significant impact regarding changes to the notes to the financial statements or internal processes as a result of the communication of KAM in the auditor's report.

Perceptions of the disclosure of voluntary additional information

8. Should the information on materiality applied in the audit be disclosed by the independent auditor?

The Brazilian and international audit standards do not address the inclusion of disclosure of materiality in the auditor's report and, for this reason, in Brazil, the audit reports do not include this voluntary disclosure. However, there are some countries that allow the voluntary disclosure of materiality due to local laws, a fact that has been generating discussion and expectations in the countries where the auditors have not voluntarily adopted such communication.

We note that most of the board members that answered this survey totally agree (53.2%) or partially agree (23.4%) with the inclusion of the voluntary disclosure of materiality in the independent auditor's reports. For the remaining board members (23.4%), the topic is not relevant to be mentioned by the auditor.

9. Should the inclusion of observations and/or indications of the result of the audit procedures in the description of how the matter was addressed be mandatory when communicating a KAM?

Most of the responding board members (85.1%) confirmed the importance of such disclosure, indicating that it could be considered mandatory in a possible review of the audit standards arising from the PIR process (61.7% totally agree and 23.4% partially agree).

Based on the previously summarized results of the survey, we concluded that the changes made by IAASB in the audit standards on the new auditor's report were well-accepted by the surveyed group, evidencing the importance of the auditor's report. We did not identify the need for significant changes in the structure of the current format of the report. However, we would like to point out some aspects that deserve the attention of IAASB in this PIR process for the auditor's report to remain relevant and reliable, with an adequate process of communication between the company's auditors, investors and those charged with governance.

Although the new expanded auditor's report has reached the purpose of being more informative, providing more clarity to the audit process and responsibilities, there is room for improvements in the way to communicate the KAM. We suggest that the readability aspects of KAM may be analyzed and discussed in the PIR process, including disclosure of additional guidance or educational to auditors that addresses aspects regarding how to avoid standardizations and repetitions of matters in the following years after first-time adoption, among others mentioned in question 5 above. With respect to the disclosure of additional information, we would suggest that IAASB take into consideration in the PIR process the requirement to disclose in the KAM the observations and/or indication of results of the audit procedures in all KAM communications, since such disclosure has already been adopted by some auditors. With respect to the voluntary disclosure of materiality, although there is a perception that such disclosure provides further transparency to the audit performed, it should be taken into consideration the main purpose of the audit, which is to increase the level

of trust in the financial statements by users, by means of an opinion on the financial statements: whether they were prepared and are following a proper presentation structure. At what extent voluntary disclosures on materiality can be considered useful information for decision making by the users of the financial statements?

Additionally, there is a risk of misinterpretation by those not familiar with the audit standards, with the acceptable quantitative materiality benchmarks, that also take into consideration qualitative analysis in the determination of materiality. We would suggest that such matter may be addressed by IAASB in the PIR process.

Sincerely,

Maria Patricia Agostineto
Master Student
Controllership and Corporate Finance
CCSA – *Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie*

Prof. Dr. Liliane Cristina Segura
Advisor
Controllership and Corporate Finance
CCSA – *Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie*

Appendix:

Table 1: General perceptions on the auditor's report

Question	Frequency		
	Yes	No	Total
1) What is the extension of your reading of the auditor's report?			
- I read the entire report.	39	8	47
- I only read the auditor's opinion and the KAM	8	39	47
2) Does the new auditor's report provide better understanding and transparency for the work carried out by the independent auditor and their responsibilities?	45	2	47
3) Did the new auditor's report positively change your perception of the quality of the audit performed?	38	9	47

Source: survey data

Table 2: General perceptions of the extent information on the auditor's report

Question	Frequency				Total
	Very useful	Useful	Limited value	Not useful	
4) In your view, to what extent is the following information provided in the new auditor's report useful?					
- Communication of the key audit matters	35	9	3	-	47
- Changes to the presentation of the auditor's report (for example, the opinion section starts to be presented at the beginning of the report)	19	19	8	1	47
- When applicable, a separate section to address matters related to going concern	27	18	1	1	47

Source: survey data

Table 3: Specific perceptions about KAM and disclosure of voluntary additional information

Question	Frequency					Total
	Totally agree	Partially agree	Indifferent	Partially disagree	Totally disagree	
5a) Based on the reports that you have been reading, has the information communicated in KAM met your expectations?	17	27	2	1	-	47
5b) Based on the reports that you have been reading, indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:						
- The description of KAM is concise, that is, properly summarized	22	23	2	-	-	47
- The description of KAM is understandable, without being excessively technical	20	24	1	2	-	47

Question	Frequency					Total
	Totally agree	Partially agree	Indifferent	Partially disagree	Totally disagree	
- The description of KAM is specific to the entity, without generic and standardized wording	20	18	4	5	-	47
- Has the communication of KAM changed the way this matter had been handled and disclosed in the notes to the financial statements?	19	20	3	3	2	47
6) Based on the auditor's reports you have been reading, which matter do you consider more relevant and useful to be communicated as KAM?						
- When related to accounting estimates	23	21	2	1	-	47
- When related to a higher risk of material misstatement	36	9	1	1	-	47
- When related to facts and transactions that took place in the year	20	23	4	-	-	47
7) Has the communication of KAM affected internal processes such as, for example, the improvement of the internal control and the preparation of the financial statements by management?	15	19	10	2	1	47
8) Should the information on materiality applied in the audit be disclosed by the independent auditor?	25	11	2	3	6	47
9) Should the inclusion of observations and/or indications of the result of the audit procedures in the description of how the matter was addressed be mandatory when communicating a KAM?	29	11	5	1	1	47

Source: survey data

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DECLARAÇÃO DO ESTRATO DO PTT.

Para melhor documentar e apresentar os produtos técnicos/tecnológicos (PTT) elaborados pelo corpo docente e discente do PPG-CFTG, o NDE criou uma comissão composta de docentes permanentes, com o objetivo de analisar e recomendar melhorias quanto ao impacto, inovação, complexidade, aplicabilidade, abrangência e replicabilidade.

Embasados no descritivo e nas justificativas apresentadas pelos autores do presente PTT quanto aos aspectos indicados acima (impacto, inovação, complexidade, aplicabilidade, abrangência e replicabilidade), os examinadores Jose Carlos Tiomatsu Oyadomari e Adilson Carlos Yoshikuni analisaram sua adequação e apresentaram sugestões de melhoria. Após a implementação dos ajustes sugeridos, os autores e os examinadores concordam que o PTT se enquadra na classificação TA3.

Transformação causada pelo produto técnico/tecnológico no ambiente (organização, comunidade, localidade, etc.) ao qual se destina. Necessário declarar o motivo da criação, a relevância da questão do demandante e o foco de aplicação do produto. Avalia-se o impacto potencial e realizado do produto ao ambiente de transformação ao que se destina.											
Critério de avaliação	Realizado			Potencial			Replicável			TOTAL	
	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Pontos	Pond.
IMPACTO (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Ausência de impacto	8	4,8	Pontos Ausência de impacto	10,0	4				8,8	14,7
APLICABILIDADE (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Não aplicada	8	3,2	Pontos Não aplicável	10,0	2	Pontos Não Replicável	10	4,0	9,2	15,3
INOVAÇÃO (Peso: 25%)	Sem inovação	15	15,0							15,0	25,0
COMPLEXIDADE (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Não complexo	10	10,0							10,0	16,7
								Estrato	TA3	Pontuação	71,7